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Beyond Anesthesia: A Mini Review of Virtual Reality as an Adjunct in Urological Procedures

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Beyond Anesthesia: A Mini Review of Virtual Reality as an Adjunct in Urological Procedures

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Abstract

For selected endourological interventions, local anesthesia provides an alternative to general anesthesia and can avoid complications and reduce turnover times and health care costs. Virtual reality (VR) has emerged as a promising nonpharmacological adjunct with potential to improve local anesthesia tolerability. This mini-review examines the role of VR during urological procedures under local anesthesia. Ten studies were included from 559 screened articles. For more invasive procedures, VR use was often associated with significant pain and anxiety reductions, while other studies reported minimal effects. VR effectiveness varied according to the invasiveness of the procedure, patient anxiety, and VR content. While VR shows potential in urology, further research is needed to confirm its effectiveness across various interventions.

Patient summary: We reviewed studies on the use of virtual reality to reduce pain and anxiety during urological procedures. The current evidence shows promise, but more studies in urology are needed in this emerging field.

1. Introduction

Effective pain management is crucial for enhancement of patient satisfaction and outcomes during medical procedures. For selected endourological interventions, local or regional anesthesia offers a viable alternative to general anesthesia and can reduce anesthetic complications and costs, and improve scheduling flexibility and turnover times. Notably, sooner scheduling of procedures may improve oncological outcomes, as timely interventions are often critical in cancer treatment. In recent years, virtual reality (VR) has emerged as a promising nonpharmacological tool for pain management by diverting the patient's attention from painful stimuli via immersive experiences. Lower costs and better accessibility have made VR a viable adjunct distraction for procedures such as venepuncture, childbirth, minimally invasive surgeries, and changes of burn dressings (1). However, VR use in urological interventions remains underexplored. This mini-review examines the role of VR as a distraction method during urological interventions under local or regional anesthesia in adults.

A comprehensive PubMed search was conducted for retrospective, prospective, and randomized controlled trials (RCTs) examining the impact of VR on clinical outcomes in urological interventions. Of 559 articles identified, ten met the eligibility criteria and were included in this review. The ten studies (1199 patients) consisted of three prospective cohort studies and seven RCTs, with sample size ranging from 30 to 270 participants (Table 1).

2. VR use during urological procedures

2.1. Prostate biopsy

Two studies examined the effect of VR during prostate biopsy (PBx). The first RCT divided 96 men scheduled for transrectal ultrasound-guided PBx into three groups: VR goggles, stress balls, and usual care (2). The VR group reported significantly lower pain scores (mean Visual Analog Scale [VAS] score 5.18 vs. 6.84; $p < 0.05$) and had better vital signs than the control group (2). Similarly, a two-arm (VR vs standard of care [SOC]) prospective cohort study with 153 men undergoing magnetic resonance imaging-guided PBx found that VR in addition to a periprostatic nerve block (SOC) significantly reduced pain in a PBx-naïve cohort (mean VAS score 2.7 vs 3.8; $p = 0.012$) (3).

2.2. Rigid cystoscopy

Two studies focused on VR use during rigid cystoscopy. A two-arm RCT with 159 patients undergoing rigid cystoscopy under local anesthesia revealed lower heart rate variability (6.29 vs 11.09 beats/min; $p < 0.001$), shorter procedure time (5.33 vs 8.65 min; $p < 0.001$), and lower pain (mean VAS score 3.26 vs 4.33; $p = 0.023$) in the VR versus the control group (4). Another RCT involving 103 patients found that the VR group had lower pain scores (mean numeric rating scale [NRS] score 4.3 vs 5.1; $p = 0.049$; mean Adult-modified Face, Legs, Activity, Cry, Consolability Scale score 1.3 vs 2.9; $p = 0.026$) but higher nausea (mean NRS score 1.8 vs 1.1; $p = 0.001$) in comparison to the control group (5).

2.3. Flexible cystoscopy

Two studies evaluated the use of VR during flexible cystoscopy. The first study randomized 270 patients into two arms: an intervention group, with a VR set, and a control group without VR. A significant reduction in anxiety (mean State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI) State Anxiety domain score 46.5 vs 50.6; $p < 0.001$) and higher patient satisfaction (mean VAS score 9.4 vs 8.8; $p < 0.001$) were observed in the VR group, although there was no significant difference in pain level ($p = 0.411$) (6). Conversely, another RCT with 45 men comparing VR goggles to SOC found no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in pain scores (mean VAS score 4.4 vs 4.3) or anxiety levels (mean VAS score 6.1 vs 5.6) (7).

2.4. Shockwave lithotripsy

A two-armed RCT with 166 patients undergoing extracorporeal shockwave lithotripsy (ESWL) revealed lower pain (mean VAS score 4.01 vs 4.94; $p = 0.011$) and higher total energy delivered (55.2 vs 48.8 J; $p = 0.037$) in the VR group than in the control group without VR, although VR did not affect comfort levels (median score of 4 for both on a 5-point Likert scale; $p = 0.301$) or clinical success ($p = 0.895$) (8). A smaller study of 30 patients proved the feasibility of VR distraction during ESWL: VR was

tolerated well (median VAS scores of 4 for postprocedural pain and 1 for anxiety) and was favored by 93% of the patients, who would recommend its use (9).

2.5. Endoscopic urological surgery

An RCT with 37 patients undergoing either holmium laser enucleation of the prostate or transurethral resection of bladder tumor under spinal anesthesia compared VR distraction to midazolam sedation (10). The VR group had lower incidence of apnea (5.6% vs 38.8%; $p = 0.042$) and higher anesthesiologist satisfaction (median Likert score of 5 vs 4 on a 5-point scale; $p = 0.005$), despite no difference in perceived pain (NRS score of 0 in both groups) (10).

2.6. Vasectomy

A prospective study involving 140 vasectomy patients compared three groups: VR goggles, two-dimensional video, and SOC (11). Although pain levels were similar among the groups (median VAS score 2), VR use was associated with higher anxiety in comparison to SOC (STAI for adults score 37 vs 34; VAS anxiety score 2 vs 1) (11).

Table 1 – Characteristics of the studies included in the review

Study	Design	Procedure	VR equipment	VR software	Key findings
Genç 2022 [2] Turkey	Three-arm RCT	TRUS PBx	VR glasses connected to a smart mobile phone	VR 360° video scenes of nature on YouTube	VR effectively reduces pain, heart rate, and diastolic blood pressure, and increases SpO ₂
Perenic 2023 [3] France	Two-arm PCS	Transrectal MRI-guided PBx	Oculus Go standalone VR with a Bose QuietComfort 35 II headset	Three landscapes: snow world, forest walk, zen garden	VR + PNB provides better analgesia than PNB alone for PBx-naïve patients undergoing transrectal MRI-guided PBx
Goergen 2022 [4] Brazil	Two-arm RCT	Rigid cystoscopy	Samsung Galaxy A5 phone with Trust Urban Exos 3D virtual reality glasses and a headset	App video simulating a ride on rails (without sudden changes that could scare or change heart rate)	VR is safe and free of side effects, is associated with less pain and discomfort, and shortens the procedure time
Łuczak 2021 [5] Poland	Two-arm RCT	Rigid cystoscopy	VR set consisting of goggles and headphones	Static image of a nature landscape (Skogafos waterfall) with dynamic animal activity, plant movement and flowing water	VR set can lower pain perception during cystoscopy, but may cause moderate nausea
Ketsuwan 2022 [6] Thailand	Two-arm RCT	Flexible cystoscopy	Head-mounted display (BOBOVRZ6, Winhoo, Guangdong, China) with an Apple iPhone 12 smartphone	Landscape image of snowy mountain with relaxing background music	VR is a simple, economical, and effective modality for reducing anxiety and enhancing satisfaction during flexible cystoscopy
Walker 2014 [7] USA	Two-arm RCT	Flexible cystoscopy	VR helmet and track-ball hand controller	SnowWorld: patients shoot snowballs at penguins, robots, and igloos	VR distraction had no benefit in mitigating pain for male patients during cystoscopy
Weynants 2023 [8] Belgium	Two-arm RCT	SWL	Sedakit VR goggles (Oncomfort SA, Wavre, Belgium) with a visual and audible 3D environment	Underwater view following the tail of a whale to induce relaxation	VR allows higher energy levels during treatment while maintaining comfort levels, but this did not improve clinical success
Candela 2023 [9] France	One-arm PCS	SWL	HypnoVR (Strasbourg, France) helmet allowing virtual visual and auditory experiences	Six 3D videos showing relaxing places accompanied by specific musical compositions, hypnotic narratives, and suggested controlled breathing and cardiac coherence	Initial patient reports are positive regarding pain and anxiety tolerance
Moon 2018 [10] South Korea	Two-arm RCT	Endoscopic urologic surgery	Head-mounted display and earphone connected to an Android cell phone (Samsung Galaxy 7.0, Seoul, Korea)	VR underwater ocean view while listening to narrations designed to induce relaxation and meditation (Aqua 30 Korean v4.0, Oncomfort SA)	VR distraction is preferable to midazolam sedation in terms of patient and anesthesiologist satisfaction
Dings 2021 [11] The Netherlands	Three-arm PCS	Vasectomy	Samsung gear VR glasses	Four short 360° movies: three on nature (North Pole, dolphins underwater, safari), one "slow TV" (couple finding a home)	Neither VR nor 2D video glasses reduced pain or stress; higher anxiety levels and longer procedure time in the VR group

2D = two-dimensional; 3D = three-dimensional; MRI = magnetic resonance imaging; PBx = prostate biopsy; PCS = prospective cohort study; PNB = periprostatic nerve block; RCT = randomized controlled trial; SpO₂ = oxygen saturation; SWL = shockwave lithotripsy; TRUS = transrectal ultrasound; VR = virtual reality.

3. Discussion

The studies we reviewed reveal the potential of VR to reduce pain and anxiety across urological interventions, albeit with mixed results. VR showed greater effectiveness in reducing pain during more invasive procedures such as PBx and rigid cystoscopy. Conversely, for less invasive procedures such as flexible cystoscopy, the impact of VR was more pronounced for anxiety rather than pain relief. This discrepancy may be attributed to two main factors. First, the varying levels of perceived discomfort and anxiety associated with procedure invasiveness offer more opportunity for VR to make a significant impact in more invasive cases. Second, the smaller absolute effect size for less invasive procedures means that larger sample sizes are needed to detect statistically significant differences, underscoring the importance of adequately powered studies.

Interestingly, VR showed no significant effects during vasectomy. This may be because the intervention and population potentially negate the calming effects of VR. Furthermore, VR efficacy may vary according to the technology and content used. While enhanced telepresence and immersion are observed with high-tech in comparison to low-tech VR, resulting in a significant reduction in pain (12), active VR, which involves user interaction, has been associated with greater pain relief and higher pain tolerance and thresholds in comparison to passive VR (13, 14). However, systematic reviews found no significant difference for the latter (1, 15).

Our findings indicate that the effectiveness of VR in urological procedures depends on factors such as procedure invasiveness, patient anxiety levels, demographics, and VR technology and content. Its proven efficacy in reducing pain and anxiety during needle-related and minor procedures under local anesthesia (1, 16) supports the suitability of VR for interventions such as PBx, vasectomy, circumcision, cystoscopy, and ESWL (17). Tailoring of VR to specific procedures and patient needs is essential to maximize its potential in urology, particularly as its effectiveness may be limited in longer, more complex surgeries that require deeper sedation (16, 18).

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